

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Some N-Halogeno-Polynitroaryl Rhodanines

S. P. GUPTA and (MISS) PREM DUREJA

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Meerut

Manuscript received 31 January 1973; revised 5 February 1974; accepted 22 July 1974

Some N-substituted polynitrophenyl rhodanines have been prepared either by the condensation of sodium chloroacetate and N-substituted aryl ammonium-dithiocarbamate or by the interaction of halogenonitrobenzenes and 4-thiazolidinones. They have been characterised and tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Colletot richum gleosporides* by spore germination method. A relation between fungi-toxicity and structure has also been established.

RECENTLY N-substituted-4-thiazolidinones^{1,2} have aroused much interest because of their application as anthelmintics³, nematocides⁴, fungicides⁵⁻⁸, pesticides and vulcanisation accelerators⁹. This revealed considerable scope for further work on N-substituted-4-thiazolidinones containing groups at position '3'. As a part of comprehensive survey of such compounds, we now report the synthesis and fungitoxicity of N-halogeno-polynitro phenyl rhodanines.

By the condensation of halogeno nitrobenzenes and 2-mercapto-4-thiazolidinones two products III & IV can be expected, according as the bonding takes place through nitrogen or sulphur.

But it is noteworthy that in all the cases, under the experimental conditions employed only one product in which the condensation occurs through nitrogen atom is formed. It is evidenced by the I.R. spectra of these compounds in which important modes show bands in the region 3200 cm^{-1} for NH group and 1480 cm^{-1} for C-N group. The absence of peaks in the region 1670 cm^{-1} due to C=N and 2500 cm^{-1} for SH group rules out the possibility of the structure IV. The product on hydrolysis with alkali gave the corresponding nitro anilines which further confirms their structure (III) and excludes the possibility of

the formation of IV. This is in agreement with the observations of Dains¹⁶. The bands in the region 1710 , 1350 and 800 cm^{-1} are due to C=O, NO₂ and Cl atom respectively. Alternatively identical compounds have been obtained by the condensation of sodium chloro acetate and N-halogeno-nitrophenyl-ammonium dithiocarbamate (Method B)¹²⁻¹⁵.

During the present investigations the 1-chloro-2,4-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-, 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-, 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-, 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-3-methyl-, 1,2,3-trichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1,3-dichloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-, 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 1-chloro-2,4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-, and 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-benzenes on condensation with 2-mercapto-4-thiazolidone gave 3-substituted, 2,4-dinitro-, 2,6-dinitro-, 2,4,6-trinitro-, 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-, 3-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 4-chloro-2,6-dinitro-, 2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-, 2,4,6-trinitro-3-methyl-, 2,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 3-chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-, and 3-chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-phenyl-rhodanines respectively.

These compounds have been tested for their ability to inhibit the growth of *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Colletotrichum gleosporides* by spore germination method¹⁷. The dosages in $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ required for inhibition of the 50% growth of the fungi have been recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

N-Halogeno-nitrophenyl-4-thiazolidinones :

Method A : A solution of halogenonitrobenzenes (0.01 M) and potassium hydroxide (0.01 M) in ethanol

TABLE I. FUNGITOXICITY OF N-POLYNITROPHENYL RHODANINES.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{R}-\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O} \\
 | \quad | \\
 \text{S}=\text{C} \quad \text{CH}_2 \\
 \quad \quad \diagdown \quad / \\
 \quad \quad \quad \text{S}
 \end{array}$$

Sl.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur		Dosages required for inhibition of 50% growth in $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$			
					Found	Reqd.	AN	AT	HS	CG
1.	2,4-DNP	142	65	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	21.47	21.41	150	90	160	165
2.	2,6-DNP	102	75	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	21.31	21.41	95	82	145	125
3.	2,4,6-TNP	145	80	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_4\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{S}_2$	18.53	18.60	78	75	100	105
4.	2-chloro-4,6-DNP	103	70	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_4\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	19.13	19.19	85	78	95	95
5.	2-bromo-4,6-DNP	98	85	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_4\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	16.96	16.98	88	80	80	98
6.	3-chloro-4,6-DNP	138	75	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_4\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	19.26	19.19	100	150	170	160
7.	4-chloro-2,6-DNP	152	65	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_4\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	19.28	19.19	88	80	80	95
8.	4-methyl-2,6-DNP	105	70	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	20.37	20.44	95	80	90	100
9.	3-methyl-2,4,6-TNP	131	70	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{S}_2$	17.56	17.87	75	78	110	110
10.	2,3-dichloro-4,6-DNP	142	85	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_3\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	17.43	17.39	92	80	88	92
11.	2-bromo-3-chloro-4,6-DNP	186	80	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_3\text{ClBrN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	15.19	15.59	95	90	90	94
12.	2-chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	125	65	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	18.52	18.44	100	95	92	100
13.	2-bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	129	60	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	15.92	15.96	110	98	95	100
14.	3-chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	119	70	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	18.47	18.44	122	150	130	145

DNP and TNP refers to dinitro and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected.

AN, AT, HS and CG refers to *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Colletotrichum gloeosporoides* respectively.

was added dropwise to a solution of 4-thiazolidinones (0.01 M) in ethanol (10 ml). The mixture was then refluxed for about four to five hours. On cooling the product that separate out is crystallised out of acetone.

Method B: Carbon-di-sulphide (18.9 g) was added to concentrated ammonia (30 ml) cooled in an ice bath. It was followed by substituted anilines (28 g) added in small quantities over a period of fifteen minutes. The dithiocarbamate salt precipitated was allowed to stand overnight. It was then filtered, washed and dried.

The solution of sodium chloroacetate was prepared by mixing cooled solutions of chloroacetic acid (19 g) in water (20 ml) and sodium hydroxide (7 g) in water (20 ml). It was then treated with anhydrous sodium carbonate until the solution was basic. The solution of sodium chloroacetate is stirred and cooled to 5°-10° and the N-substituted ammonium dithiocarbamate was added during a period of ten minutes. The stirring was continued while the flask was allowed to warm to room temperature. The solid mass that separate out was treated with a warm solution of concentrated hydrochloric acid (66 ml) in water (26 ml). The mixture was heated to 80°-90° for fifteen minutes. On cooling the solid mass was separated, washed and crystallised out of acetone.

Their m.p., yield and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

Results and Discussions

The fungitoxicity of N-nitrophenyl-4-thiazolidinones depends on the nature, position and the electro-

nic influences of the substituents in the phenyl ring. Halogen atom and the nitro group at the ortho or para position to the N-phenyl linkage increases fungitoxicity, and it is more pronounced when present in the ortho than in the para position presumably due to -I effect. The toxicity is further increased by the introduction of the third nitro group in the position 4 and 6. A halogen atom at the meta position seems to decrease fungitoxicity due to the absence of its -T effect. Out of the two halogens studied the activating influence of chlorine is more than that of bromine. The effect of methyl group is rather anomalous, when present at ortho and meta position in the phenyl ring it decreases toxicity where as at para position increases it.

The electronegative character of nitro group and halogen atom causes withdrawal of electron from the rhodanine ring resulting in its opening at 1S-5C linkage to give dithiocarbamate ion, which reacts with the active component of the living tissue thus destroying their contribution to the life process¹⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R., for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (P.D.). Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for the I.R. spectra and C, H analysis.

References

1. F. C. BROWN and C. K. BRADSHAW, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 384.
2. B. K. RAVAL and J. J. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 58.
3. T. BACTELLI, U.S. Pat. 2,784,196, May 5, 1957.
4. J. R. GEIGY, Fr. Pat. 1,395,069, April 9, 1965.
5. G. J. M. VAN-DER KERK and H. L. KLOPPING, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1951, **70**, 917.
6. F. C. BROWN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 6189.
7. J. KINUGAWA and K. NAGASE, Jap. Pat. 8542, May 4, 1965.
8. B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 939.
9. F. A. V. SULLIVAN and A. C. LINDAW, Belg. Pat. 640429, May 26, 1964.
10. N. K. SUNDHOLM and J. B. SKAPTASON, U.S. Pat. 2,510,725, June 6, 1950.
11. H. TRIPATHY and R. N. DASH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1232.
12. L. ARAPIDES, *Ann.*, 1888, **28**, 249.
13. B. HOLMBERG, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1910, **81**, 451.
14. F. B. DAINS, R. Q. BREWSTER and C. P. CLANDER, *Org. Syn. Coll. Vol. I*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1941, 447.
15. C. E. REDEMANN, R. N. IOKE and G. A. ALLES, *Org. Syn. Coll. Vol. III*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1955, 363.
16. F. B. DAINS, R. IRVIN and C. G. HARREL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 613.
17. H. B. S. MONTGOMERY and M. H. J. MOORE, *Pomol. Hort. Sci.*, 1938, **15**, 258.
18. G. J. M. VAN-DER A. KERK and KAAR SIJPESTELJIM, Medadal Land bouwhogeschool opzoekingssta, Staat. Gent., (1953), **18**, 402.